

ACOUSTIC AND ACOUSTOOPTICAL PROPERTIES OF LANGASITE CRYSTALS

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Abstract. *In this article, the author discusses the problems associated with the development of acoustoelectronic devices for modern information and communication systems. Using the acousto-optical method, acousto-electronic materials from the langasite group are studied. Crystals were measured for their elastic and photoelastic constants, as well as their nonlinear parameters. The anisotropy of photoelastic properties of Langasite crystal was studied and relevant results were obtained. The effective section of the Acousto-optical quality factor (M_2) was determined for this crystal.*

Keywords: *LGS crystals, acousto-optica, Dixon method, piezoelectric, acoustic waves, photoelastic constant.*

АКУСТИЧЕСКИЕ И АКУСТООПТИЧЕСКИЕ СВОЙСТВА КРИСТАЛЛОВ ЛАНГАСИТА

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор рассматривает проблемы, связанные с разработкой акустоэлектронных устройств для современных информационно-коммуникационных систем. Акустооптическим методом исследованы акустоэлектронные материалы группы лангасита. Кристаллы были измерены на предмет их упругих и фотоупругих констант, а также нелинейных параметров. Изучена анизотропия фотоупругих свойств кристалла Лангасита и получены соответствующие результаты. Для этого кристалла было определено эффективное сечение акустооптической добротности (M_2).*

Ключевые слова: *кристаллы LGS, акустооптика, метод Диксона, пьезоэлектрик, акустические волны, фотоупругая константа.*

LANGAZIT KRISTALLARINING AKUSTIK VA AKUSTOOPTIK XUSUSIYATLARI

Abstrakt. *Ushbu maqolada muallif zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya tizimlari uchun akustoelektron qurilmalarni ishlab chiqish bilan bog'liq muammolarni muhokama qiladi. Akusto-optik usuldan foydalanib, langazit guruhidagi akustoelektron materiallar o'rganiladi. Kristallar elastik va fotoelastik konstantalar, shuningdek, ularning chiziqli bo'lmagan parametrlari uchun o'lchandi. Langazit kristalining fotoelastik xossalari anizotropiyasi o'rganilib, tegishli natijalar olindi. Ushbu kristall uchun akusto-optik sifat omilining (M_2) samarali bo'limi aniqlandi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *LGS kristallari, akusto-optika, Dikson usuli, pyezoelektrik, akustik to'lqinlar, fotoelastik doimiy.*

Introduction. The langasite family of crystals ($\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$, LGS) has attracted much attention and has been extensively studied [1 -5].

Acoustic waves are strongly attenuated by these compounds at room temperature (several times lower than in quartz) and they do not phase transition between their melting points (1300–1500 °C [6]).

Further, LGS-type crystals are non-pyroelectric, show temperature stability of physical properties, possess relatively high electromechanical coupling coefficient and show piezoelectric response even at temperatures very close to the melting point [6]. LGS-type crystals are commonly used in the acoustic electronics industry because of their unique combination of properties.

Despite the huge number of scientific publications devoted to crystals of the langasite group, the problem of measuring the constants (elastic, piezoelectric, etc.) is still relevant. The relevance and novelty of the work performed lies both in the constants obtained as a result of measurements and in the use of a unique acousto-optical method. The research work carried out has shown the effectiveness of the application of

acousto-optical methods in the study of materials used for both acoustoelectronic and acousto-optical devices.

The efficiency of acousto-optical measurements depends on the level of photoelastic constants of the crystal; therefore, it is necessary to know the matrix of these coefficients. The measurement of the main components of the matrix of photoelastic coefficients was carried out by the comparison method (Dixon method) using fused quartz as a reference material.

The acousto-optical method makes it possible to measure the propagation velocities of acoustic modes in selected directions and planes of the crystal. The most accurate method for measuring the velocity of acoustic modes (pulse-phase) can be implemented in the acousto-optical version under certain conditions. In addition, optical visualization of the angular distributions of reciprocal velocities of acoustic modes for selected observation planes is possible, which makes it possible to obtain a complete set of elastic moduli of the crystal using a minimum number of samples.

Materials and Methods. The experiments were conducted on lithium niobate samples with crystallographic axes of [100] and [001]. By using quartz piezoelectric transducers with X- or Y-cuts, light on acoustic waves of 400–1200 MHz was diffraction measured using the Bragg diffraction method. The light source was a helium-neon laser ($\lambda_0=632.8$ nm). An acoustic polarization analyzer was used to determine the direction of polarization of the light beam incident on the sample. We used the modified Dixon-Cohen method [8] to measure the effective photoelastic constants. Both the reference sample and the test sample were attached to piezoelectric transducers.

The intensity values of light diffracted in the reference I_{1e} and test sample I_{1x} were measured when acoustic waves were excited from the reference side. The I_{2x} sample and I_{2e} standard were then excited with acoustic waves and their light intensities were measured again. The diagram of the method, when acoustic waves are excited from the sample side, is shown in Fig. 1 Where 1 is a standard sample, 2 is a sample under study, 3 is a piezoelectric transducer, q is the wave vector of sound, k_1 and k_2 are the wave vectors of incident and diffracted light, respectively, I_0 is the intensity of the incident light, θ_B is the outer angle of Bragg diffraction. I_{1x} and I_{1s} – intensity of light diffracted in the sample and standard, respectively, when sound propagates from the sample to the standard;

I_{2x} and I_{2s} are the same luminous intensities as sound propagates from the standard to the sample.

The velocity values of acoustic waves along the [100] and [001] axes necessary for the calculation were determined from the angle of Bragg diffraction of light at these waves with an accuracy of approximately 0.2% [9]. The accuracy of determining the value of M_2 relative to the standard was about 20%.

Figure 1. Scheme for determining photoelastic constants using the Dixon method [12]

Based on the measured intensities of diffracted light in lithium niobate samples for various directions and polarizations of light and acoustic waves, the effective photoelastic constants p_{eff} and the acousto-optical quality factor M_2 were calculated. In particular, the influence of the orientation of the wave vector of light in these crystals on the acousto-optical figure merit M_2 was studied [7]:

$$M_2 = \frac{n_1^3 n_2^3 p_{\alpha\beta\phi}^2}{\rho V^3}, \quad (2)$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the refractive indices of the incident and diffracted light, respectively, ρ is the density, V is the speed of the acoustic wave.

The effective photoelastic constant, p_{eff} in relations (1) and (2) is the convolution of the values of the components of the photoelastic tensor p_{ijkl} according to the normalized polarization vectors, respectively, of diffracted and incident light α and β , and the direction and polarization of the acoustic wave κ and γ [5]:

$$p_{\alpha\beta\phi} = p_{ijkl} \alpha_i \beta_j \gamma_k \kappa_l, \quad (3)$$

Thus, the coefficient M_2 depends on the geometry of diffraction of light by sound and allows one to evaluate the acousto-optical properties of materials. By changing the direction of the wave vector and polarization of the incident light relative to the wave vector and polarization of the acoustic wave, one can influence the value of the effective photoelastic constant and, ultimately, control the efficiency of Bragg diffraction of light.

For calculations, we used experimental values of the speed of acoustic waves, relations (1), (3) and data on density and refractive indices from [9]. The results of calculating the components of the photoelastic tensor (in matrix notation) together with the main characteristics of these crystals are given in Table 1. The wave vectors q and k indicate the crystallographic direction of propagation of acoustic and light waves, respectively, β is the direction of polarization of the incident light.[11]

Results. Based on the measured velocities of acoustic waves in the chosen directions of the crystal, the components of elastic moduli were calculated and the angular distributions of acoustic velocities for the main crystallographic planes were calculated. On fig. Figure 2 shows the calculated data for the (100) plane of the LGS crystal. The inner contour corresponds to the reciprocal velocity of the quasi-longitudinal mode, and the outer contours define the angular distributions of the reciprocal velocities of the two quasi-transverse modes. The anisotropy of the effective photoelastic constant in the (100) plane of the Langasite crystal is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Angular distributions of reciprocal velocities of acoustic modes in the (100) plane of an LGS crystal. 1) transverse 2) transverse 3) longitudinal wave

Figure 3. Anisotropy of the effective photoelastic constant of the crystal for longitudinal acoustic waves propagating in the (100) plane in an LGS crystal

Conclusion. The value of the maximum effective photoelastic constant for the LGS crystal was found to be equal to $p_{\text{eff}}=p_{33}=0.16$ ($\varphi=90$) for a longitudinal acoustic wave propagating along the X axis (in the direction of light polarization). The refractive index $n_3=n_e = 1.9107$ and the velocity of the longitudinal acoustic wave $V_3 = 6785$ m/s correspond to the value of this effective photoelastic constant. Entering p_{eff} , n_3 , V_3 and density $\rho = 5733$ kg/m³ into (1), we calculate $M_2 = 0.67 \cdot 10^{-15}$ s³/kg.

Thus, even though the maximum values of effective photoelastic constant and acousto-optical quality factor measured for LGS crystal are several times lower than those of crystals used in modulators of ultrasonic ranges, these results are basic data for determining the acousto-optical properties of other crystals of the Langasite family can be.

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